

Heterocyclic Compounds. Part IX. Synthesis of Some Indole Derivatives

J. R. Merchant and S. S. Salgar

Two new indole derivatives, 4,5,7-trimethoxyindole and 4,5,6-triethoxyisatin, have been synthesised. Methods for the preparation of 4-, 5- and 6-benzindoles and 5-chloroindole have been modified.

In course of some synthetic work it became necessary to prepare indole derivatives substituted in the benzene ring. As a result, the hitherto unknown 4,5,7-trimethoxyindole (A) and 4,5,6-triethoxyisatin (B) have been synthesised.

The starting material for the synthesis of (A) was *o*-vanillin which on Elb's persulphate oxidation afforded the known 2,5-dihydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde¹. Methylation of the latter furnished 2,3,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde which on being condensed with nitromethane yielded the known β -nitrostyrene derivative. When the latter was nitrated with fuming nitric acid at 0°, 6- β -dinitro-2,3,5-trimethoxystyrene was obtained. Reduction of the latter with iron filings² in acetic acid afforded the indole (A) in 20% yield as a colorless solid.

The isatin derivative (B) was synthesised using gallic acid as the starting material, the triethyl ether³ of which on treatment with thionyl chloride afforded 3,4,5-triethoxybenzoyl chloride⁴. The acid chloride was converted into the corresponding amide by treatment with ammonia. The amide on Hofmann's reaction⁵ gave the known⁶ 3,4,5-triethoxyaniline. The latter was condensed with ethyl oxomalonate⁶ to yield the intermediate product (II) which on oxidation gave red crystals of the isatin derivative (B) in about 5% yield.

1. Merchant *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4142.

2. Burton and Duffield, *ibid.*, 1949, 78.

3rd Mouthner, "Organic Syntheses" Coll. vol. I, 1944, p. 537.

4. Laesle and Jordan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 805.

5. Buck and Ide, "Organic Syntheses", Coll. vol. II, 1953, p. 44.

6. Dox, *ibid.*, Coll. vol. I, 1944, p. 266.

4,5-Benzindole and 6,7-benzindole were prepared by the periodate oxidation of the intermediate benzoquinoline derivatives. The method of preparation of these by the condensation of naphthylamines with epichlorohydrin, as described by Pennington *et al.*⁷, was modified by carrying out the reaction with equimolecular quantities of the reactants in ethanolic solution in presence of a few drops of hydrochloric acid.

Similarly, 5-chloroindole⁸ was prepared by the periodate oxidation of the unknown 3-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-6-chloroquinoline which in turn was obtained by the condensation of epichlorohydrin with *p*-chloroaniline.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-β-Dinitro-2,3,5-trimethoxystyrene.—To a suspension of 2,3,5-trimethoxy-β-nitrostyrene⁷ (1.25 g.) in glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was added gradually fuming nitric acid (3.80 ml, *d* 1.5) so that the temperature did not rise above 0°. After the addition of nitric acid was completed, the reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 2 hrs. Dilution with water gave a solid which on crystallisation from ethanol furnished yellow needles, m.p. 143-44°, yield 0.45 g. (Found : N, 9.8. C₁₁H₁₀O₇N₂ requires N, 9.86%).

4,5,7-Trimethoxyindole (A).—The above nitro derivative was dissolved in boiling acetic acid (80 ml, 80%) and to the hot (not boiling) solution iron powder (20 g.) was added in portions to maintain a steady ebullition and until the reddish brown colour formed disappeared. The solution was then decanted into aqueous sodium hydrogen sulphite

7. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 565.

8. Rydon and Long, *Nature*, 1949, 164, 575; cf. *Chem. Abs.*, 1950, 44, 1095.

(100 g. in 500 ml.) in a large separating funnel and the mixture well shaken. The resulting mixture containing much suspended solid was extracted with ether until it gave negative Ehrlich's reaction. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and the solvent removed under vacuum. The crude indole was crystallised from dilute ethanol and further purified by sublimation under vacuum to clusters of colorless needles, m.p. 124° , yield 0.6 g. It gave a red coloration with Ehrlich's reagent in cold. (Found: N, 6.9. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 6.76%).

4,5,6-Triethoxyisatin (B).—To a solution of 3,4,5-triethoxyaniline (0.2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (1.3 ml) was added with stirring ethyl oxomalonate⁸ (0.2 g.). The resulting olive-green solution was heated on a steam bath for 1 hour and then kept for 2 hours at room temperature. Diluting the solution with water (30 ml) and then adding solid ammonium carbonate to give a final pH 8 yielded a brown oil. It was extracted with ether, the extract washed with water, and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The brown oil obtained after removal of the ether was treated with a 5% NaOH solution (3 ml) and the solution filtered. The yellow filtrate was heated on a water bath and a stream of air passed through it for 10 minutes. The resulting dark yellow solution was brought to pH 4 by dropwise addition of formic acid (95%). An orange microcrystalline solid separated on keeping in a refrigerator. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol in red needles, m. p. 170° , yield 15 mg. It gave the characteristic blue colour reaction⁹ with thiophene and H_2SO_4 . (Found: N, 5.0. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 5.02%).

3-Hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-7,8-benzoquinoline Hydrochloride (III).—To a solution of α -naphthylamine (7.65 g., 0.05 ml) and epichlorohydrin (4.93 g., 0.05 ml) in ethanol (40 ml, 70%) was added a drop or two of HCl (conc.) and the mixture left at room temperature for 3 days. An ether extract of the reaction mixture was taken and the dark oil obtained after removal of the ether was refluxed with bromobenzene (400 ml) for 48 hours. After cooling it was extracted with 10% HCl solution and the acid extracted was evaporated to dryness. The brown solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol-ether mixture; the hydrochloride m.p. 245° (decomp.), yield 6.5 g. Vorozhtsov and Kutkevichus¹⁰ reported m.p. 245° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.6. Calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONCl}$: N, 9.42%).

6,7-Benzindole (IV) was prepared by oxidation of the hydrochloride (III) with sodium periodate in presence of NaOH, according to the method described by Pennington *et al.*⁷ White crystals from dilute ethanol were obtained, m.p. $171-72^\circ$. It gave a very strong positive test with Ehrlich's reagent. (Found: N, 8.8. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}$ requires N, 8.38%).

3-Hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-5,6-benzoquinoline hydrochloride (V) was prepared from β -naphthylamine and epichlorohydrin, as described above, as yellowish crystals, m.p. 240° (decomp.), yield 6.5 g. (Found: N, 9.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONCl}$ requires N, 9.42%).

4,5-Benzindole (VI) was prepared by oxidation of the hydrochloride (V) with sodium periodate in presence of NaOH, as described by Pennington *et al.*⁷ It was obtained as an oil, b. p. $148-50^\circ/5$ mm. (Found: N, 8.6. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}$ requires N, 8.38%).

9. Langenbeck *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1894, 512, 276; Kalb and Berrer, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 2105.

10. *Zhur. Obch. Khim.*, 1957, 27, 2521; *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, 52, 6338, 7317.

3-Hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-6-chloroquinoline Hydrochloride.—The condensation of equimolar quantities of *p*-chloroaniline and epichlorohydrin, as described above, gave yellowish shining crystals from ethanol-ether, m.p. 134-36°. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_9H_{11}ONCl$, requires N, 6.36%).

*5-Chloroindole*⁸ was prepared from the chloroquinoline hydrochloride by oxidation with sodium periodate. It was obtained as colorless needles on crystallisation from water, m.p. 69-70°.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY-1.

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